

Intravenous versus Intramuscular Magnesium Sulfate for the Management of Severe Preeclampsia and EclampsiaAravapalli Sridevi¹, G. Sumathi², B. Aparna³¹Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, MNR Medical College & Hospital, Sangareddy, Telangana²Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, MNR Medical College & Hospital, Sangareddy, Telangana³Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Maheshwara Medical College & Hospital, Isnapur, Patancheru, Telangana

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Abstract:

Introduction: Eclampsia and preeclampsia are two of the leading causes of maternal mortality. If not treated promptly and effectively, eclamptic convulsions can be fatal emergencies with a significant risk of morbidity and death. One of the most important eclampsia management principles is controlling convulsions. When treating eclampsia, magnesium sulfate is the gold standard for anticonvulsant activity. This study was designed to assess the efficacy of intravenous versus intramuscular magnesium sulfate in severe preeclampsia and eclampsia cases.

Materials and methods: A total of 116 pregnant women with eclampsia, imminent eclampsia, or severe preeclampsia were randomly allocated to two groups and managed with Pritchard regimen (Group 1) and Zuspan regimen (Group 2). Serum magnesium levels, maternal complications, neonatal outcome and status of seizure recurrence was reported.

Results: The most prevalent mode of delivery was LSCS in 58.62% of group 1 and 62.06% of group 2. The APGAR scores were 6.44 and 6.70 at 1 minute, and 8.08 and 8.39 after 5 minutes. The average birth weight was 2.47 kg in group 1 and 2.30 kg in group 2. Seizure recurrence was observed in 5.17% of cases in group 1 and 1.72% in group 2. Abruption (8.65%) and HELLP (8.62%) were the most prevalent maternal complications in group 2.

Conclusion: The magnesium sulfate regimens administered intramuscularly and intravenously are equally beneficial in reducing the negative effects experienced by both the mother and the foetus. In contrast to intravascular infusion of magnesium sulfate, which carries a lower risk of toxicity, intramuscular magnesium sulfate is unpleasant and has a poorer compliance rate.

Keywords: Preeclampsia, Magnesium Sulfate, Foetal outcome, Modified Bishop's Score.

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Introduction

Eclampsia, a hypertension condition of pregnancy, affects 1.4% of women at delivery, while preeclampsia affects 4.6% of women [1]. Fetal and maternal mortality are possible outcomes of these conditions, which are marked by proteinuria, high blood pressure, and seizures (once eclampsia has developed) [2,3].

Globally, low- and middle-income nations have a maternal mortality rate that is about 200 times greater due to preeclampsia and eclampsia than high-income countries [4,5]. Nearly 9% of the world's 63,000 annual fatalities occurred in Africa and Asia [6,7]. The World Health Organization (WHO) states that magnesium sulfate (MgSO₄) is the best medication for extreme pre-eclampsia and

eclampsia prevention and management [8,10,11]. To treat severe pre-eclampsia and eclampsia, the World Health Organization recommends a 24-hour intravenous/intramuscular regimen consisting of a loading dose and maintenance doses [9]. Administration of MgSO₄ to women should only take place in healthcare facilities that have sufficient personnel and clinical resources to monitor them for symptoms of magnesium toxicity in between doses [12].

Although magnesium sulfate is useful in preventing and treating eclamptic seizures, the ideal maintenance medication duration and therapeutic regimen remain uncertain. Hence, this study was conducted to assess the efficacy of intravenous

versus intramuscular magnesium sulfate in severe preeclampsia and eclampsia cases attending tertiary care teaching hospital.

Material and Methods

This prospective interventional study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at MNR Medical College and Hospital, Sangareddy and Maheshwara Medical College, Isnapur from April 2022 to June 2024. Antenatal mothers attending and admitted to department of Obstetrics and gynaecology with severe pre-eclampsia and imminent eclampsia irrespective of age, parity, gestational age and willing to participate were included. Women with non-severe pre-eclampsia, chronic hypertension, seizures, cerebrovascular complications, meningitis, cardiac conduction and not willing to participate were excluded. Written informed consent was obtained from all the participants and study protocol was approved by the institutional ethics committee.

Two groups of 116 pregnant women with eclampsia, imminent eclampsia, or severe preeclampsia were randomly selected. Group 1 patients were given an intravenous loading dose of 4 gm MgSO₄ for 3-5 minutes, followed immediately by an intramuscular injection of 10 gm 50% MgSO₄. After birth, a maintenance dose of 5 grams of magnesium sulfate (MgSO₄) is given intramuscularly every 4 hours for a total of 22 grams to the gluteal region over a 24-hour period (Pritchard regimen). Group 2 patients were given 4 gm MgSO₄ intravenously for 15 to 20 minutes. Following delivery, a maintenance dose of 1 gramme of magnesium sulfate per hour via infusion pump is provided for 24 hours, total of 44 grams (Zuspan regimen). Regular investigations were conducted, as well as a full physical, clinical, and

systemic examination of each abdomen and pelvis. The participants' obstetric and clinical histories were collected. The height of the uterine fundus, the occurrence of contractions, and the viability of the foetus were all assessed per abdomen. A vaginal examination was performed using aseptic techniques. The Modified Bishop's Score is used to assess the cervix's favourability. Blood samples were collected for the Renal Function Test, Liver Function Test, and Complete Blood Count. Urine flow was instantly detected and monitored hourly after the patient was catheterized with Foley's indwelling catheter. Proteinuria was determined using a urine sample. The delivery method was determined based on the foetus viability, modified bishop score, and gestational age. Labor was induced with prostaglandin gel (PGE₂) or mechanical induction using Foley's catheter. Neonatal outcome, APGAR score, and baby weight were recorded. Following the delivery of MgSO₄, the complete blood count and renal function tests were repeated. Regular home blood pressure checks, whether performed by the patient or a visiting healthcare professional, are encouraged. If the symptoms persist, an OPD review should be conducted within three to five days. Every preeclamptic patient should be closely monitored for three months, including advice on antihypertensive medication and regular checks. It is suggested that they use contraception for at least two or three years. An IUCD is the suggested strategy. SPSS 26.0 was used to analyse the collected data. The data was displayed using frequencies and percentages. The chi-square test was employed to compare the two groups. A p-value of less than 0.05 indicated that the result was statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Sociodemographic details of study participants.

Sociodemographic data	Group 1 (n=58)		Group 2 (n=58)		p-value
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
Age (In years)					
Below 21	04	6.90%	02	3.44%	1.265
21-30	42	72.41%	46	79.31%	
Above 30	12	20.68%	10	17.24%	
Gravidity					
Primi	27	46.56%	36	62.06%	0.822
Multi	31	53.44%	22	37.97%	
Gestational age (In weeks)					
< 28	-	-	01	0.17%	1.962
29-36	38	65.51%	46	79.31%	
>36	20	34.48%	11	18.96%	
BMI (Kg/m²)					
≤18.5	17	29.31%	14	24.13%	0.674
18.5 – 25	21	36.20%	23	39.65%	
25 – 29.9	13	22.41%	15	25.86%	
≥30	07	12.06%	06	10.34%	
Booking status					
Booked	57	98.28%	54	93.10%	1.053
Not Booked	01	1.72%	03	5.17%	

Graph 1: Hemodynamic parameters among study participants (mm of Hg).

Graph 2: Distribution of cases as per types of pre-eclampsia.

Table 2: Laboratory investigations among study participants.

Parameter	Group 1 (n=58)		Group 2 (n=58)		p-value
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
Urine albumin					
Trace 1+	06	10.34%	08	13.80%	1.032
2+, 3+, 4+	32	55.17%	28	48.27%	
Loaded	20	34.48%	22	37.93%	
Serum creatinine	0.852±0.367		0.893±0.518		1.026
Serum magnesium	7.752±0.898		7.031±0.973		0.028

The difference of urine albumin and mean difference of serum creatinine was statistically not significant (p>0.05). But, mean difference of serum magnesium was statistically significant (p<0.05).

Table 3: Details of perinatal outcome and seizure recurrence.

Parameter	Group 1 (n=58)		Group 2 (n=58)		p-value
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
Mode of delivery					
NVD	23	39.65%	20	34.48%	0.0315
LSCS	34	58.62%	36	62.06%	
Forceps	-	-	01	1.72%	
Vacuum	01	1.72%	01	1.72%	
Foetal outcome (Perinatal mortality)					
Present	03	5.17%	01	1.72%	0.874
Absent	55	94.82%	57	98.28%	
APGAR score					
At 1 minute	6.44±1.892		6.70±1.045		0.0473
At 5 minutes	8.08±3.217		8.39±2.033		0.0194
Birth weight	2.47±0.485		2.30±1.182		1.562
NICU admission					
Admitted	29	50%	24	41.37%	0.0612
Not admitted	29	50%	34	58.62%	
Seizure recurrence					
Present	03	5.17%	01	1.72%	
Absent	55	94.82%	57	98.28%	

Graph 3: details of maternal complications.

Discussion

The majority of participants were between the ages of 21 and 30 (72.41% in group one and 79.31% in group two). The majority of individuals (36.20% in group 1 and 39.65% in group 2) reported a BMI of 18.5–25 kg/m², followed by overweight (22.41% in group 1 and 25.86% in group 2) and obese (12.06% in group 1 and 10.34% in group 2). Group 1 booked 98.28% of participants, while group 2 scheduled 93.10% (Table 1). A Study by Kanti V et al., on 82 cases reported that 17.7% of cases were booked in IV group while 12.19% of cases in IM group and remaining cases were unbooked. Similar

findings were reported by Sahu et al. (2014) with a range of 84%-92% of unbooked cases [13, 14].

Majority participants were primigravida in cumulative of both groups, which was similar to the findings of Ekel et al. (2005) reported it to be 89% while Seth et al. (2010) found incidence of eclampsia in primigravida to be 74.2% [15, 16]. The majority of participants (65.51% in group 1 and 79.31% in group 2) were between 29 and 36 weeks of gestation, followed by those over 36 weeks (34.48% in group 1 and 18.96% in group 2). A Study by Kanti V et al., reported a mean

gestation age of 36.11 weeks in intravenous group and 35.31 weeks in intra muscular group [13].

The majority of individuals had severe eclampsia (43.10% in group 1 and 51.72% in group 2), followed by impending eclampsia, postpartum eclampsia, antepartum eclampsia, and intrapartum eclampsia (Graph 2). A study by Kanti et al., reported that 88.23% of cases had antepartum and intrapartum eclampsia, while 11.76% had postpartum eclampsia. Similarly study by Bangal et al., reported antepartum in 60%, intrapartum in 28% and postpartum eclampsia in 12% of cases [17]. Group 1 had significantly higher mean systolic and diastolic blood pressures than group 2 ($p < 0.05$) (Graph 2). A study by Kanti et al., reported the mean SBP was 174.44 mm of Hg and 173.22 mm of Hg and mean DBP was 110.98 mm of Hg and 110.24 mm of Hg in IM group and IV groups respectively [13]. Coetzee EJ et al., on 822 women with severe preeclampsia found mean SBP of 173 mm of Hg and DBP of 116 mm of Hg [18].

The most prevalent mode of delivery was LSCS in 58.62% of group 1 and 62.06% of group 2, followed by normal vaginal delivery in 39.65% of group 1 and 34.48% of group 2 patients. The APGAR scores were 6.44 and 6.70 at 1 minute, and 8.08 and 8.39 after 5 minutes. The mean difference in APGAR scores was statistically significant. The average birth weight was 2.47 kg in group 1 and 2.30 kg in group 2. Group 1 admitted 50% of its children and Group 2 admitted 41.37% to the NICU. Seizure recurrence was observed in 5.17% of cases in group 1 and 1.72% in group 2 (Table 3).

Abruption (8.65%) and HELLP (8.62%) were the most prevalent maternal complications in group 2. Graph 3 shows that 5.18% of patients in group 1 had PNMR, CVT, and abruption. A study by Kanti et al., reported thrombocytopenia was common complication in 9.75% of IV and IM cases, followed by PPH, abruptio and acute renal failure [13]. A study by Sardesai et al., reported that disseminated intravascular coagulopathy was common in both groups followed by pulmonary oedema, HEELP, ARF and cerebral haemorrhage [19].

Pascoal ACF et al., reported that magnesium sulfate therapy at the maintenance dose of 1 gram/hour was just as effective as the 2-gram maintenance dose, with fewer side effects to prevent eclampsia in pregnant and postpartum women with severe preeclampsia [20]. Chissell S et al., reported that no significant differences between groups with regard to clinical outcome of either mother or child. Similar average serum magnesium concentrations were produced by the regimens the only significant difference was that fluctuations in magnesium levels were greater with the IM than the i.v. regimen. None of the patients had seizures

despite levels mostly below 2 mmol/l [21]. Okusanya BO et al., stated that Zuspan and Pritchard regimens indicate that the minimum effective serum magnesium concentration for eclampsia prophylaxis is lower than the generally accepted level [22]. Sibai BM et al., stated that the intravenous regimen with a maintenance dose of 1 gm/hr is inadequate in management of preeclamptic patients [23].

Conclusion

The magnesium sulfate regimens administered intramuscularly and intravenously are equally beneficial in reducing the negative effects experienced by both the mother and the foetus. The majority of Indian women are thought to have low to normal BMIs and thus can get by with a lesser dosage of magnesium sulfate (Zuspan: 28g; Pritchard: 44g). In contrast to intravenous infusion of magnesium sulfate, which carries a lower risk of toxicity, intramuscular magnesium sulfate is unpleasant and has a poorer compliance rate.

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